

Presidential Address*

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LET me take this opportunity of conveying my sincere gratefulness to all the members of the Society who have done me a great honour by electing me as the President of the Indian Chemical Society, which is one of the oldest scientific societies of the country. The Society has already established a reputation for itself by publishing a regular monthly journal for more than half a century and providing a forum for the chemists of the country to work together. Indian chemists, therefore, owe a deep debt of gratitude to the founding fathers like Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray who established the Society and directed its activities in the initial stages. Let me crave your indulgence in thinking aloud with you whether we have been able to live up to the expectations of the pioneer members who did so much for the development of the Society on sound lines.

The first deficiency that should strike us is the rate of growth of the fellowship of the Society. Although the number of chemists working in different academic and other fields of the country has increased manifold during the last 2-3 decades, yet the fellowship of the Society has not been able to keep pace with this rate of growth at all. By contrast the chemists throughout the world have been one of the most active groups of scientists in organising their national societies. For example, the American Chemical Society in U.S.A., the Chemical Society in U.K. and the Gesellschaft Deutscher Chemiker in Germany, are the most flourishing scientific societies of their countries. Apart from the huge membership of these societies, they have taken a keen interest in organising symposia bringing a large number (the annual conventions of the American Chemical Society are generally attended by more than 10,000 chemists) of chemists working in academic and applied fields together and have thus assisted considerably the development of chemical education and research in their respective countries.

For the initial first four decades, the annual sessions of the Indian Chemical Society used to be held at the time of the sessions of the Indian Science Congress. It has been fortunate that during the last one and a half decades, the annual conventions of the Indian Chemical Society have been arranged separately and later on these Conventions have received cooperation from other organisations of chemists like the Institute of Chemistry and the Society of Biological Chemists. These annual conventions have been quite successful in bringing together a large number of chemists and one of the most attractive features of these conventions has been to provide an opportunity to younger chemists to present their research work before the peers in the field.

In view of the growth in the number of chemists and the rapid pace at which the chemical research and education have developed in the country, I hope that I am voicing the feelings of all of my colleagues here, that it is an opportune moment to take stock of our achievements so far and think of the directions in which we should try to expand activities of the society in order that these keep pace with the progress of the chemistry in the country. Soon after taking over the Presidency of the Society, I had circulated a letter to some friends drawing their attention to the following directions in this connection :

(i) Improvement of the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society to the international standards.

(ii) A more comprehensive scheme of lectures at various centres and organisation of periodical discussions and symposia etc. (establishment of active branches in different centres would be of great help in this direction).

(iii) Initiating dialogues and (if possible) a Journal of Chemical Education.

(iv) Bringing together workers in academic and applied fields of Chemistry.

(v) Organising International Conferences so that the Society plays an effective role in the activities of the IUPAC.

I am happy to place on record the enthusiastic response that I received from almost all the friends to whom I addressed this circular and it is my earnest desire that the Society should take effective steps to channelise its activities in some of these new directions. Apart from strengthening the Society, this should attract a greater number of chemists and thus create an atmosphere of enthusiasm all around.

One of the most significant contributions of any professional society is the Journal which provides an opportunity to scientists in that discipline for publication of their original research work. I am sure all of you will agree with me that through the dedicated efforts of Editors and Editorial Boards, the standard of the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society has considerably improved during the last 4-5 years both in the format as well as in the quality of printing. The standard of the research papers also has increased substantially. In spite of this, if we compare it with the Journals of many other active societies, in the world, there appears to be room for considerable improvement. Unfortunately, many of us continue to send our better

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work for publication in foreign journals. There may be justifiable reasons for this as the manuscripts tend to receive not only more enlightened refereeing and more rapid publication in these foreign journals, but also attract the attention of a wider circle of chemists due to the larger circulation of many of these foreign journals. However, this is a vicious circle and has to be broken. It is only when we publish our better papers in our own journals that the quality and reputation of our national journals would be enhanced and they will receive due attention from chemists not only in this country but throughout the world. A recent symposium arranged jointly by the three Academies of Science in the country has tried to focus the attention of all our scientists in these directions.

I crave your kind patience in reciting a personal experience which should reduce our doubts about the attention that the work published in our journal is able to receive. The example I have chosen would enable me to follow the practice conventionally adopted in Presidential addresses of describing a few research efforts of mine which have given me some satisfaction. Incidentally, this would also provide me an opportunity of discussing briefly some problems of chemical research faced by younger research workers in the country and the role that the society could play to assist them.

In 1953-54, I had published two papers^{1,2} on Aluminium Alkoxides in the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society. In these publications, I had tried to resolve a considerable amount of confusion in the earlier literature about the complexity and molecular association of these academically interesting and industrially useful compounds. For example, a simple product like aluminium isopropoxide had been reported in the earlier publications by reputed authorities to depict a molecular association varying from 1 to 7. However, in these two papers, I had shown under carefully controlled conditions that aluminium isopropoxide is dimeric in the vapour phase, but condenses to a colourless highly viscous liquid, which shows trimeric behaviour in refluxing benzene. This trimeric liquid slowly polymerises further to a tetrameric solid which is more stable in nature. Further polymerisation to higher forms does occur, but is much slower. On the other hand, it was shown that if alcohols with more ramified or branched alkoxy groups are taken, the resulting alkoxide (eg. tertiary butoxide) becomes a dimer and remains so not only in the vapour state but also in the liquid and solid forms.

In the interchange of ethoxy or isopropoxy groups of these lower aluminium alkoxides with other alkoxy groups under the general heading of alcoholysis and transesterification reactions, it was shown that the alkoxides of aluminium have two types of alkoxy groups which can be called 'terminal' and 'bridging' respectively. In the interchange reactions with higher normal alcohols, all the alkoxy groups of the lower alkoxide were readily interchanged. However, in the interchange reactions with ramified alcohols, the terminal groups were interchanged with a much greater facility than the bridging groups. For example, in the interchange

of the isopropoxy groups of aluminium isopropoxide with tertiary butoxy and amyloxy groups, it was shown that two of the isopropoxy groups per aluminium atom are exchanged with great facility, but the replacement of the third one becomes slower by a factor of 100 or even more. A number of new mixed alkoxides, e.g., $Al_2(OEt)_2(OBu^t)_4$, $Al_2(OEt)(OBu^t)_5$ and $Al(OPr^i)_3(OAm^t)_4$ were thus described and plausible structures were suggested for all of them. Unfortunately, I did not have the instrumental facilities available to be able to confirm my own suggestions. I have, however, been lucky that beginning with the work of Shiner, *et al*³ in 196, almost all these suggested structures have been confirmed by Worrall and coworkers⁴ in early seventies using N.M.R. spectroscopy. More recently, we have also been able to throw more light on these structures⁵ by physicochemical work in our laboratories also.

In spite of being published in our own journal, these first two papers of mine in the Journal of Indian Chemical Society on aluminium alkoxides appear to have attracted considerable attention, as immediately after their publication I received a very large number of requests from chemists in many parts of the world for sending them reprints. Being a lecturer in a University with a meagre salary of about Rs. 300 per month and with no departmental support available for the despatch of reprints etc., I could not accede to the requests of more than a few of these people. Fortunately the position is a little better now as contingency grants are available in the schemes sanctioned by a number of sources but a little more systematic arrangement in this direction is desirable.

In 1961 when I was on a lecture tour in U.S.A., I had an unplanned halt for a few hours at Cleveland due to missing a plane connection. In view of this, I thought of contacting on phone the research section of M/s Harshaw Chemical Company, which I knew to be the largest producer of aluminium isopropoxide in the world. As soon as my contact was established and I mentioned my name, I was surprised that the Research Director asked me whether I was the same Mehrotra who had published work on aluminium alkoxides in the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society about 7-8 years ago. The Director then showed a keen interest in my discussions with some of their research staff and I readily accepted their invitation. During these discussions, I was told that the firm had a serious problem. This was about some samples of aluminium isopropoxide (mostly aged) that they were supplying to their customers. The research department had tried to look into the matter and found that the samples which these firms found defective showed correct analyses, but sometimes during distillation in large columns under vacuum, these samples did not appear to distil at all although the temperature of the still was much higher than the distillation temperatures of aluminium isopropoxide at that particular pressure. However, after long waiting in some cases, the sample suddenly flooded over the column. I could immediately see the source of this difficulty and told them that the results that I had published in the Journal of Indian Chemical Society supplied a clue to the solution of their problem also.

Unfortunately they did not have an actual copy of the paper but had read the results only in the Chemical Abstracts. When I explained to them that according to my observations in the aforesaid paper, the difficulty may be ascribed to a slow continued further polymerisation of their samples on ageing during storage. Such polymerised samples would require a much higher amount of heat of depolymerisation. Such samples, therefore, although their analyses would be in exact correspondence with those required theoretically for pure aluminium isopropoxide, may not distil readily and may require some time and energy for their depolymerisation. If, therefore, during their distillation, the temperature was raised rather rapidly, no distillation may occur initially but the heat thus available would depolymerise the samples which would then flood over all of a sudden, as the temperature of the still might have been raised higher than the actual boiling point of the trimeric aluminium isopropoxide at that pressure. Having understood the basic difficulty, the solution I suggested was a very simple one. If the heating of such a sample was carried out slowly at a temperature slightly below the recorded distillation temperature at that pressure, the sample would be depolymerised and then would distil over in a normal manner when the temperature was slowly raised a few degrees above the boiling point. As the suggestions appeared to have removed the difficulty and complaints of many of their customers, the firm was extremely happy and grateful for this simple but effective solution.

Regarding the improvement of the journal, I would like to mention another facet of the problem. If we can improve the quality of the journal at this moment, our Indian Chemists would be more easily prompted to publish their good work also in our own journal now. We all know that a number of foreign journals have imposed a per page printing charge which is almost impossible for us to bear from our meagre research grants even if the foreign exchange was available. This is, therefore, a psychological moment when the chemists in the country can be attracted to our own journal and we should try to take maximum advantage of this extraneous factor also.

Apart from the improvement of the Journal, the Society should take a much greater interest in the improvement of chemical education in the country. The American Chemical Society has a division of chemical education and their Journal of Chemical Education has established a great reputation for itself throughout the world. Under the auspices of the National Council of Science Education, we had undertaken the publication of the Indian Journal of Chemical Education but unfortunately due to a number of difficulties its publication has been stopped during the last 2-3 years.

Another direction in which the Society must strive gradually but constantly is to bring chemists working in the academic field and the industry together. The Society was publishing an Industrial Edition of the Journal till a few years ago. I am not suggesting a re-publication of this journal itself, but the Society must devise some

plans of enhancing its activities in applied fields to be able to attract research and other chemists working in the industry also to its fold. Apart from an increment in the membership of the Society, bringing together the chemists working in the teaching institutions, the research establishments and the industries together to a common platform would be a great service in itself. Development of chemical industry is absolutely essential today for the technological growth of any country. It is fortunate that in addition to the National Chemical Laboratory, a number of other Regional and other specialist (e.g., CECRI, CGCRI, CSMCRI, CFRI, CFTRI, NML, CDRI, IIP, ITRC, ATIRA, SASMIRA, etc.) laboratories in India are mainly concerned with problems of chemical industry. In spite of sporadic efforts at various levels, our teaching and academic research institutions have not been deeply involved with the work of immediate national relevance being pursued in the above laboratories. I am one of those who continues to believe that the Universities should concentrate on frontier line research of fundamental importance, but in the choice of areas of emphasis, national relevance and importance should be one of the major factors. More often than not, we are merely following the fashions of the west in which directions also, our research efforts are often limited (mainly due to lack of proper facilities) to jotting an 'i' or crossing a 't' in some paper published from foreign laboratory. In view of the narrowing gap between scientific discovery in the laboratory and its exploitation in industry, it would be of great national importance if the academic research workers are to be at least aware of the applied potentialities of their research findings and keep a constant eye on the possibility of their exploitation. The Society could be of great service by providing a channel of communication amongst chemists working in different directions in the country.

Apart from the above, one of the major responsibilities of any professional society should be to project a correct image of the profession to the public. This has assumed a special significance in recent years in view of a disenchantment from physical sciences due to problems of environment, etc. Chemistry and chemical industry are sometimes given a major blame in these directions. These factors have led to a lowering of enrolment figures of quality students in a large number of institutions even in developed countries. Although the needs of developing countries like ours are entirely different, yet unfortunately in a shrinking world of today, the infection appears to be percolating here as well. This has among other effects, lowered the employability of our graduates and has thus initiated a vicious circle which would not be beneficial to the country or to our profession in the long run.

The contribution of the Society in encouraging chemical research in the country in the initial stages by providing a medium of publication and a platform for discussions has been of considerable importance. There has been undoubtedly a significant improvement in the quality of work being carried out both in our universities as well as in other research institutions. However, the work in many of these establishments does suffer

considerably due to non-availability of sophisticated instrumentation. This situation has to be improved and the Society should play a dynamic role in advising the Government and other agencies about the same. The nature of chemical research has altered considerably during the last two decades. Even though problems may be merely of a synthetic nature, establishment of the identity of products requires confirmation from a variety of sophisticated techniques involving a large number of costly instruments. In spite of attention being focussed on this problem for the last 1-2 decades, it is only recently that some efforts are being made for providing central instrumentation facilities at a few centres. These should be augmented considerably and a more significant precaution would be to see that these facilities are made available easily to all the chemists in the country. Apart from the import of sophisticated instruments from abroad, the real solution would lie in the development of our own capabilities in devising new techniques and equipment. I am sure that we would all agree that the chemical research schools in our country are exceptionally weak in these areas. Although a few workshops were arranged in this direction a few years ago, there is hardly any provision even now in most of our institutions for giving training to chemists in electronics instrumentation and sometimes even in simple glass-blowing and other workshop activities.

On the other side, very few research groups of chemistry in the country are working on theoretical problems of a high order. This is rather surprising in view of very flourishing schools of theoretical research in our country in the areas of Physics and Mathematics. Work in theoretical Chemistry, as in many other fields now, would require availability of computer facilities and this is another essential need to which attention of the planners and the Government has to be drawn.

Apart from the academic-industrial interphase in which chemistry has to play a highly significant role, it has to pervade many new fields and areas in order to retain its pivotal position amongst all the branches

of science. The chemist of today has already moved into a number of new interdisciplinary areas. The physical chemist delves as deeply into quantum mechanics and spectroscopic theories as his colleagues in the physics department do. The geochemist studies moon rocks and the atmosphere of the Mars. The inorganic chemist is deeply interested in the role played by trace elements in the life processes. The organic chemist is all the time extending his studies deeper and deeper into more and more complex molecules which may be polymeric or bio-chemical in nature. All these trends are a happy sign of Chemistry becoming a really exciting inter-disciplinary science. The study of topics like solid state, plasma and lasers is as much a domain of Chemistry as Physics. The exciting new chemicals of heredity deserve the chemists' expert attention much more in order to help the biologists understand the mechanism of life processes. A few years ago, Dr. Lawrence E. Strong, Chairman, Division of Chemical Education of the American Chemical Society went to the extent of suggesting that it might be appropriate to give the discipline of Chemistry a new name like 'The Chemical Sciences' or 'The Molecular Sciences', in order to indicate its new multifaced dimensions.

Let me in conclusion hope that our Society will play a more positive role in providing a new sense of purpose to the efforts of Indian chemists, bringing these in tune with the modern times and making them more relevant to national development.

References

1. R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 30, 585.
2. R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 31, 85.
3. V. J. SHINER (JR.), D. WHITTAKER and V. P. FERNANDES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 2318.
4. J. G. OLIVER and J. J. WORRALL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 845.
5. R. C. MEHROTRA, *Proc. Ind. Nat. Sc. Acad.*, 1976, 42, 1.